

Role of 2,2'-Biquinolyl as a Potential Bidentate Ligand in the Stabilisation of Molybdenyl Cation in Diverse Anion Environment

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Oxohalo- and oxalato derivatives of molybdenyl cation have been synthesised using 2,2'-biquinolyl as a potential bidentate ligand. The compounds have been characterised by analytical and various other physico-chemical methods.

THE chemistry of molybdenum(V) is dominated by the oxometal ions MoO^{3+} , $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_8^{4+}$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7^{2+}$. The stability of the paramagnetic cation MoO^{3+} is dependent on both acidity of the solution and the nature of organic base present in the oxohalomolybdates (V) $\text{RH}_2 [\text{MoOX}_5]$ (where R = organic base and X = Cl or Br)^{1,2}. In the present investigations molybdenyl cation has been stabilised by $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ ions in salts and also in the neutral complexes $[\text{MoOX}_3\text{L}]$ (where L = 2, 2'-Biquinolyl)³.

In these complexes 2,2'-biquinolyl acts as both monoacidic and diacidic bases in acid medium and in solid state. These compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and other physical techniques.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Analyses :

Molybdenum¹ and halogens were estimated gravimetrically as MoO_3 and AgX respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method. Oxalate was estimated by standard³ KMnO_4 method adapted in similar compounds. Oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method.

Preparation :

2, 2' - Biquinolium oxopentachloromolybdate (V) $\text{BiquinH}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$:

A sample of about 1g of molybdenum trioxide was dissolved in 10 ml of conc. hydrochloric acid with stirring. Then 1 ml of hydroiodic acid was added and gently boiled to drive off the liberated iodine. To the concentrated small mass, minimum quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added when a bright green solution was obtained. To this solution 1.80g of 2,2'-biquinolyl dissolved in minimum quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid in the cold was added and cooled to room temperature. The immediately precipitated yellow product was filtered through sintered glass crucible and dried in vacuum desiccator over

solid KOH. Yield was about 4.8g. Found : Mo, 18.08% ; Cl, 32.81% and N, 5.45%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{H}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$: Mo, 18.20% , Cl, 33.65% and N, 5.30%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.00.

2, 2' - Biquinolium oxotetrachloromolybdate (V) $\text{BiquinH} [\text{MoOCl}_4]$:

About 1.60g of the salt $\text{BiquinH}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$ were refluxed with 40 ml of dehydrated ethanol for 3 hrs. The salt gradually dissolved to give a yellow solution from which solid greenish yellow product appeared on final cooling. This was filtered, washed twice with dehydrated ethanol and dried to constant weight in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. The yield was about 1.20g. Found : Mo, 18.67% ; Cl, 27.71% and N, 5.83%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{H} [\text{MoOCl}_4]$: Mo, 18.79% ; Cl, 27.79% and N, 5.47%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.98.

Oxotrichloro (2,2'-biquinolyl) molybdenum (V) $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Biquin}]$:

A sample of about 0.8g of $\text{BiquinH} [\text{MoOCl}_4]$ was heated in a tube furnace at 125° in the dry carbon dioxide atmosphere till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceases. The colour of the compound changed from greenish yellow to dark green product. Yield was found to be about 0.74g, supporting the theoretical weight loss of 7.14%. Found : Mo, 20.20% ; Cl, 23.68% and N, 5.43%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_3]$: Mo, 20.25% ; Cl, 22.37% and N, 5.90%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.05.

2, 2'-Biquinolium oxodichloroquo oxalato molybdate (V) $\text{BiquinH} [\text{MoOCl}_2 \cdot \text{OX} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$:

A sample of about 0.6g of $\text{BiquinH} [\text{MoOCl}_4]$ was mixed with about 0.16g of powdered oxalic acid in 1 : 1 mole ratio and the mixture was heated at 150° in a tube furnace in dry carbon dioxide atmosphere till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceases. The brown coloured product was washed with minimum quantity

of dehydrated ethanol to free from excess unreacted oxalic acid, filtered in glass crucible and dried to constant weight in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yield was about 0.4g. Found : Mo, 17.71% ; Cl, 13.28% ; N, 4.90% and $C_2O_4^{2-}$, 15.82%. Calcd. for BiquinH [MoOCl₂.OX.H₂O] : Mo, 17.58% ; Cl, 13.02% ; N, 5.12% and $C_2O_4^{2-}$, 16.11%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.9.

2, 2' - Biquinolium oxopentabromomolybdate (V) [BiquinH₂ [MoOBr₅]] :

About 1g of molybdenum trioxide was dissolved in 10 ml of hot 48% hydrobromic acid with stirring and concentrated to a pasty mass. To the small mass further 10 ml of concentrated hydrobromic acid added and concentrated. The operation was repeated till a clear yellow solution of oxopentabromo molybdic (V) acid was obtained. Then 1.8g of 2,2'-biquinolyl dissolved in minimum quantity of hydrobromic acid were added to this yellow solution with stirring. Orange yellow crystalline solid separated out on cooling to room temperature. It was filtered through sintered glass crucible and was dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yield was about 5g. Found : Mo, 12.63% ; Br, 52.7% and N, 3.54%. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₈N₂.H₂[MoOBr₅] : Mo, 12.46% ; Br, 51.90% and N, 3.63%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.03.

2, 2' - Biquinolium oxotetrabromomolybdate (V) [BiquinH [MoOBr₄]] :

About 1.60g of the salt BiquinH₂ [MoOBr₅] were refluxed with 40 ml of dehydrated ethanol for 3 hrs. The salt gradually dissolved to give a brown solution from which solid yellowish brown product appeared on final cooling. This was filtered, washed twice with

dehydrated ethanol and dried to constant weight in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. The yield was about 1.20g. Found : Mo, 13.82% ; Br, 45.38% and N, 3.63%. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₈N₂H [MoOBr₄] : Mo, 13.93% ; Br, 46.44% and N, 3.98%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.97.

Oxotribromo (2, 2'-biquinolyl) molybdenum (V) [MoOBr₃.Biquin] :

A sample of about 0.7g of BiquinH [MoOBr₄] was heated in a tube furnace at 170° in the dry carbon dioxide atmosphere till the evolution of hydrogen-bromide ceases. The colour of the compound changed from yellowish brown to greenish brown product. Yield was found to be about 0.60g, supporting the theoretical weight loss of 11.75%. Found : Mo, 15.68% ; Br, 39.50% and N, 4.22%. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₈N₂[MoOBr₃] : Mo, 15.78% ; Br, 39.45% ; N, 4.60%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.86.

Conductivity measurements :

Molar conductances of the non-electrolytes [MoOX₃.Biquin] were measured in a "dip type" conductivity cell using distilled nitrobenzene as solvent. The values for [MoOCl₃.Biquin] and [MoOBr₃.Biquin] are 3.01 ohm⁻¹cm² and 5.13 ohm⁻¹cm² respectively. The values are much less than those for binary electrolyte⁴ (ΛM_2 for 1:2 electrolyte in 10⁻³ M nitrobenzene solution ranges from 20-30 ohm⁻¹cm² mole⁻¹) which indicate the non-electrolytic nature of the compounds. Due to the decomposition of the salts BiquinH₂ [MoOX₅] and BiquinH [MoOX₄] in water, conductance measurements were not possible in aqueous medium.

TABLE 1—IR BANDS IN CM⁻¹

Compounds	Main bands (cm ⁻¹)
BiquinH ₂ [MoOCl ₂]	780w, 810w, 840s, 980vs, 1160m, 1230m, 1275vw, 1310vw, 1345m, 1400s, 1425vw, 1530w, 1640s.
BiquinH[MoOCl ₂]	760m, 780w, 800vw, 840s, 920w, 980vs, 1170vw, 1220m, 1285vw, 1310vw, 1395m, 1440vw, 1515w, 1550m, 1610vs, 1630w.
[MoOCl ₂ .Biquin]	730m, 750w, 805vs, 850vw, 895vw, 960s, b; 1070vw, 1120w, 1200m, 1280vw, b; 1360s, b; 1410vw, 1515m, 1580vs, 1610vw, sh.
BiquinH ₂ [MoOBr ₅]	770vw, 830vs, 960vs, 1080vw, b, 1160s, 1230m, 1270vw, 1300w, 1340m, 1390vs, 1415w, 1485w, 1515wb, 1590m, 1640m.
BiquinH[MoOBr ₄]	720w, 750w, 770w, 830s, 870vw, 970vs, 1090vw, b; 1150w, b, 1215m, 1300w, 1340w, 1390s, 1540m, b; 1600vs, 1620m, sh.
[MoOBr ₄ .Biquin]	750m, 780m, 820vs, 870w, 905vs, 940s, 970w, 1090w, 1140w, 1210w, b, 1340m, 1390s, b, 1430m, 1500m, 1595bs, 1630w, b.
BiquinH[MoOCl ₂ .OX.H ₂ O]	740m, 790m, 820s, 860w, 900m, 940w, sh; 960m, 1130m, 1205m, 1290w, 1330m, 1380s, 1420w, 1500m, 1530m, 1590vs, sh, 1650vs, b; 3425mb.

m=medium ; vw=very weak ; s=strong ; vs=very strong ; b=broad ; sh=shoulder.

TABLE—2

Compounds	λ_{max} in m μ	ν ($\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$)	Molar extinction ϵ	Assignments
1	2	3	4	5
1. Biquin H ₂ [MoOCl ₅] in DMF	730	13.7	13.00	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	339	29.5	17,580	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	327	30.6	22,340	³ B ₂ → ³ E (III)
	315	31.8	20,100	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	268	37.3	27,080	³ B ₂ → ³ E (III)
2. Biquin H[MoOCl ₄] in DMF	720	13.9	16.00	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	339	29.5	15,340	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	326	30.7	19,540	³ B ₂ → ³ E (III)
	314	31.8	17,900	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	268	37.3	28,880	³ B ₂ → ³ E (III)
3. [MoOCl ₅ .Biquin] in DMF	720	13.9	9.00	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	339	29.5	15,960	L → Mo
	326	30.7	20,200	Charge transfer
	315	31.8	18,100	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	267	37.5	24,900	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (II)
4. Biquin H[MoOCl ₃ .OX.H ₂ O] in DMF	610	16.4	5.00	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	339	29.5	14,720	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	326	30.7	18,990	³ B ₂ → ³ E (III)
	315	31.8	17,050	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	269	37.2	19,840	³ B ₂ → ³ E (III)
5. Biquin H ₂ [MoOBr ₅] in acetonitrile	475	21.05	430	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	415	24.1	1,530	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	325	30.8	22,300	³ B ₂ → ³ E (II)
	313	31.9	19,900	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	258	38.7	73,600	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (II)
	229	43.7	31,700	³ B ₂ → ³ E (III)
6. Biquin H[MoOBr ₄] in acetonitrile	469	21.32	410	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	414	24.1	1,660	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	325	30.8	24,600	³ B ₂ → ³ E (II)
	313	31.9	22,000	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	258	38.7	79,800	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (II)
	229	43.7	30,200	³ B ₂ → ³ E (III)
7. [MoOBr ₅ .Biquin] in acetonitrile	690	14.5	450	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	345	28.9	14,600	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	325	30.8	18,700	L → Mo
	314	31.8	16,600	Charge transfer
	258	38.7	59,700	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	229	43.7	20,400	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (II)

Magnetic susceptibility measurements :

The magnetic susceptibilities of the compounds were measured in Gouy balance using a field strength of 8500 gauss. The values of μ_{eff} are 1.78(298), 1.82 (297), 1.51(300), 1.87(297), 1.55(303), 1.61(302), 1.44(302), for the compounds yellow BiquinH₂[MoOCl₅], greenish yellow BiquinH[MoOCl₄], dark green [MoOCl₃.Biquin], brown BiquinH[MoOCl₂.OX.H₂O], orange yellow BiquinH₂[MoOBr₅], yellowish brown BiquinH[MoOBr₄] and greenish brown [MoOBr₃.Biquin], respectively. Values in the parentheses represent the temperature of experiment in the absolute scale. Values of μ_{eff} are calculated as $\mu_{eff} = 2.839 (\chi'_M \cdot T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B. M. where χ'_M = corrected molar susceptibility $\chi_M - \chi_d$ (χ_M being the

uncorrected value and χ_d the diamagnetic correction for ligands). The values are in fair agreement with the d¹ configuration of Mo confirming the presence of MoO³⁺ unit in these compounds.

Ir spectra :

Ir spectra of the compounds were taken in Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. The main bands are given in Table 1. Ir spectra of the salts show strong absorption bands in the region 940-980 cm⁻¹ due to Mo(V)=O stretching vibration^{5,6}. Ir bands of the complex, BiquinH[MoOCl₃.OX.H₂O] around 1650 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra in DMF.

- I. Biquin H₂ [MoOCl₅]
- II. Biquin H [MoOCl₄]
- III. [MoOCl₃ Biquin]
- IV. Briquin H [MoOCl₃ . OX . H₂O]

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra in acetonitrile.

- V. Biquin H₂ [MoOBr₅]
- VI. Biquin H [MoOBr₄]
- VII. [MoOBr₃ . Biquin]

ν C=O stretching, 1380 cm^{-1} to the ν C-O + ν C-C stretching and 900 cm^{-1} and 1290 cm^{-1} to the ν C-O + δ (O-C=O) stretching. A broad band in this region may be assigned to the presence of coordinated water⁷.

Electronic spectra :

The solution spectra of the compounds were recorded in "Varian Series 634" UV spectrophotometer using AnalaR grade solvents. Electronic spectra of the chloro series of the compound including oxalato derivative were taken in DMF solvent and bromo series of compound were taken in acetonitrile as solvent. Results are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2. The assignments of electronic transitions are made in Table 2.

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